

CURRENT STATE OF TRAINING VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation: This article discusses the features of training volleyball players in the educational and training process. An analysis of literary sources on the issues of optimizing the educational and training process in volleyball in universities that need an urgent solution was carried out. The problem of preparing teams in higher educational institutions for sports games, in particular volleyball, is considered. The requirements that must be observed by specialists when constructing the educational and training process are described. The level of development of the basic motor qualities of students of different sports readiness and the factors determining the physical abilities of volleyball players were studied.

Key words: educational and training process, volleyball players, physical abilities, universities.

Introduction. Currently, volleyball is one of the most widespread, popular and simple sports [2, 3, 5]. Nowadays, volleyball is one of the extremely interesting and spectacular sports that needs physically trained student athletes who master technical and tactical techniques - these are power serves, powerful attacking strikes, strikes at the net and from the back line, dizzying actions in defense and timing blocking and on the court, complex technical and tactical actions with the participation of front and back line players [1, 4]. Due to its emotionality, volleyball competitions are a means of not only physical development, but also active recreation.

It is impossible to achieve high athletic results in this sport without persistent and systematic educational and training work. An analysis of literary sources shows that the peaks of sportsmanship are usually achieved by athletes who began playing the game from childhood. Correctly and professionally organized educational and training work in grassroots groups, in schools, and especially in higher educational institutions is a prerequisite for replenishing the national teams of regions and countries with young, capable volleyball athletes [9, 10, 11].

The current state of training teams in sports games, in particular volleyball, in higher educational institutions has its own difficulties and characteristics. This is due to the fact that the composition of student teams in this sport is constantly changing, namely: some athletes move from course to course, others are more technically prepared, graduate from university and drop out altogether. Problems also arise when assembling teams: insufficient level of physical, tactical, and technical preparedness. Therefore, the problem of training volleyball players in modern conditions of the educational and training process in universities is becoming quite relevant and requires finding effective ways to solve it [8].

This problem is quite widely discussed in the scientific and methodological literature. Despite the large amount of research in volleyball, many aspects of this sport remain unsolved and await improvements. People who are different in professional training, life experience, individual traits and character, temperament, etc. take part in joint sports activities, therefore the content of this sport and the psychophysiological aspects of the motor activity of players and coaches that are specifically important for volleyball are of particular relevance [11, 14].

The study of the problem of the current state of training volleyball players in the educational and training process in universities attracted the attention of psychologists, teachers, and physical education theorists: V. V. Davydov, B. T. Likhacheva. In addition, the problem of studying the structure and content of the training work of young athletes in team sports in the last decade was considered by A. V. Fedotova, G. A. Lisenchuk [12, 13].

However, it should be noted that the analyzed literature sources do not sufficiently cover ways to optimize the educational and training process in volleyball in universities and require a more effective solution to this problem.

Modern training of student volleyball players is a complex and long-term process that places high demands on the functional activity of the body, physical and technical training of athletes. The organization of the educational and training process requires high requirements, which are not limited to the training of athletes and, like the process of training a volleyball player, provides for a system of pedagogical influence on the formation of the child's personality and his physical education. [15, 16].

In the process of educational and training sessions, under the influence of physical exercises, the volleyball player develops the appropriate skills and abilities. Repeated repetition of exercises improves the overall physical condition of the body and the functioning of all organs and systems. During the educational and training process, the following tasks are solved: strengthening health, developing physical fitness, improving vital motor skills and abilities, and a correctly selected methodology for teaching volleyball contributes to the education of "volleyball" talents among students, and also creates the preconditions for the mass involvement of people of different gender and age before systematically practicing this sport throughout life [17, 18, 19].

Despite the fact that a lot of attention is paid to this issue, an analysis of the literature indicates that the majority of university students have the following physical fitness: with a score of 3 points - 41.21%; 2 points – 22.03%; 1 point – 5.88% [20].

When preparing volleyball players during the educational and training process, an important role is played by the athlete's technical training, which includes a set of techniques with which the game is played. The playing technique has the following elements: starting positions, serves, passes, offensive strikes and blocks.

In volleyball, tactical actions of players are important as a form of realizing technical potential in specific competitive activities. To achieve the set goals when preparing volleyball players, when constructing an algorithm for the educational and training process, the following should be taken into account:

- 1) the level of physical qualities and morphofunctional indicators, which largely determine the effectiveness of motor actions;
- 2) realization of physical abilities through the technique of specific playing techniques;
- 3) implementation of technical techniques through tactical actions [7, 11].

The motor actions of volleyball players consist of a large number of starts, accelerations and jumps, explosive impact movements with a long, fast and almost continuous response to changing circumstances, which places high demands on the physical fitness of volleyball players [2, 5].

The modern process of teaching and training volleyball players in higher educational institutions is subject to the laws of physical education and is built taking into account general pedagogical principles specific to sports training.

First of all, when preparing the educational and training process, volleyball players need to emphasize that during sports activities the following requirements must be observed:

- 1) systematically (at least 2 times a year) carry out medical supervision, taking into account the age characteristics of athletes, and allow only absolutely healthy children to participate in training. Strictly use medical recommendations;
- 2) divide students into groups (by age and level of training), individualize the workload. Strictly observe the daily routine, apply the principles of regularity and gradualness in increasing loads, and devote enough time to rest between loads.
- 3) do not transfer the features of the regime and methods of training adult athletes into the practice of working with children, boys and girls (highly specialized training without sufficient use of general developmental exercises and frequent use of maximum loads is prohibited) [7].

In order to correctly construct the educational and training process and determine the sports load, it is important to take into account the data of independent observations (self-monitoring) of athletes regarding their health and physical development. They allow the trainer and doctor to promptly identify unwanted changes in the body and prevent fatigue and overtraining, improve training methods, eliminate violations of the daily routine and the adverse effects of environmental factors.

The influence of volleyball-specific means on the comprehensive development and functional state of the body completely depends on the level of mastery of playing skills. Therefore, at the initial stage of the educational and training process of preparing volleyball players, exercises in technique, tactics and the game of volleyball itself do not have enough influence on the overall physical development of students. Consequently, in order for the load in classes to be optimal, it is necessary to use a certain number of general developmental and preparatory exercises [8].

The current state of training volleyball players in the educational and training process at universities involves taking into account their physical capabilities and adhering to the principle: step by step, step by step. There is a special logic to this, that is, the training of volleyball players is gradually becoming more complicated, their content is enriched. Players are given a choice: by simulating different game moments, they can increase or decrease the load. Having mastered the basic technical techniques in practice, volleyball players will not only learn how to perform them correctly, but also know exactly in what specific situation one or another technique should be used. Having mastered one level after another, you need to move on to the game. Along with the game, a certain range of technical and tactical exercises are used in the training of volleyball players, but without connection with the stage and period of the team's preparation, without taking into account the growing qualifications of the students. It is clear that such exercises subsequently become quite intensifying or even easy tasks for players, and therefore

turn out to be not a stimulating, but a restraining factor in improving sportsmanship [8, 9].

The unity of technical and tactical training is achieved by improving the technique of reception within the framework of tactical actions and repeated performance of tactical actions with increasing intensity, which helps in improving the technique. The effect of integrating these types of training is achieved through three exercises:

- first - performing game techniques within the framework of tactical actions;
- second - the gradual implementation of various tactical actions;
- third - switching in tactical actions of a different nature.

All types of exercises are characterized by the duration of their implementation. During the existence of volleyball, it was proven that the ideal technique or tactics of one player cannot be compared with the technical and tactical actions of the team.

So, the current state of training volleyball players in the educational and training process at universities includes technical and tactical training, which is one of the main ones. Game activity in volleyball is characterized by rapidly changing conditions of struggle on the court, which are under the tireless control of the opponent, who in turn tries to destroy the opponents' defense, and in the attack to impose his game plan and win.

Conclusions. Analyzing the scientific and methodological literature on this issue, it should be noted that the level of development of physical qualities and abilities specific to the game of volleyball depends on students' technical and tactical skills. The higher the level of development of special properties and capabilities, the faster you can master the basics of the technique and strategy of the game. A skillful, correct selection of methods, principles and means used in classes will help to develop skills in mastering technical techniques and tactical actions, and will contribute to the development of the physical, moral and volitional qualities of the athlete. An important stage in the methodology of the educational and training

process is the staging of training and its year-round periodization, taking into account the principles of training. In the preparation of both beginners and highly qualified volleyball players, there are periods when it is necessary to learn fundamentally new techniques, tactical actions and interactions. Therefore, there is no need for strict differentiation of the means of technical and tactical training for volleyball players who differ in their level of playing qualifications.

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